

JOS STEEL ROLLING MILL DIRECT CURRENT MACHINE SPEED CONTROL USING CLOSED-LOOP SILICON CONTROL RECTIFIER SPEED CONTROL

Chizindu Stanley Esobinenwu¹ and Lamidi Salihu Owuda²

Department of Electrical/Electronic Engineering, University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria.

Email: chizindu.esobinenwu@uniport.edu.ng and owuda@yahoo.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10965983>

Abstract: *Jos steel rolling mill plant direct current machine speed control using silicon control rectifier speed control is presented. Jos steel rolling mill is one of the three inland rolling mills established by the Federal government of Nigeria to enhance the development of steel sub-sector. As part of the ongoing efforts to revive the nation's steel industry so that the country can commence steel production. No nation can really develop without the development of its steel industry. The pivot to this development of the steel industry is through research that calls for this research in the steel industry. Rolling mills are types of metal forming machinery that process various metals through sets of roll to reduce thickness, create uniform thickness, imprint a design or compact loose material. Three types of rolling mills are two high pulls over mill that has two rolls with a constant direction of rotation around a horizontal axis, two high reversing mill that allow you to see the productivity improvement when using the two-high reversing mill and three-high rolling mill. Stress on Jos Steel Rolling Mill plant systems is increasing day by day, due to faults and sudden load change that constitutes negative threat to Jos Steel rolling mill stability. To maintained mill quality services, Study was carried out to examine the capacity and transient stability of the Jos Steel Rolling Mill. The direct current (DC) machines are electro-mechanical energy converters in which the electrical energy is exchanged with the supply load in the form of direct currents and voltages. Closed-loop silicon-controlled rectifier (SCR) which allows electricity to flow in one direction is used in a high-power control and has 3 terminal and 4 solid state layer semiconductor current controlling device, but with the added ability to be able to turn it on and off. The laboratory experiment was conducted which shows that as the rheostat 'R' was varied until armature voltage ' E_A ' = 175Vdc. Jos steel rolling mill speed of DC machine was control by changing supply voltage or the field current. The separated excited machine, the field was changed by a rheostat by power electronic means using close- loop Silicon Control Rectifiers Speed Control. While the shunt machine a variable resistor was introduced in the shunt circuit. The field was weakening and the*

speed increased for smooth Jos steel rolling mill operation. The effect upon the dc machine speed and the armature voltage ' E_A ' shows that at low DC machine speed, the armature conduct late. The highest speed obtained was 3540 rev/min before the DC machine turned 'OFF'. To provide filtration for the smooth operation of the DC machine in Jos Steel Rolling Mill, Silicon control rectifier (SCR) reactance " X_L " filter choke was incorporated and connected to terminal 3 and 10 of the SCR to provide filtration for the smooth operation of the DC machine in the Jos Steel Rolling Mill to prevent heavy armature transient surge current. A Silicon control rectifier capacitor " C_2 " the electrolytic filtering capacitor was connected across the dc machine and the armature winding was connected to terminal 8 and 1. This is because, the capacitor have to discharge through armature winding when the SCR is not conducting and for the smooth running of the DC machine, the terminal 8 and 11 was used for the smooth operation of the dc machine instead of terminal 8 and 1. The capacitor absorbs the current peak during each cycle rather than the armature and the dc machine vibrate cooler than before. Experiment on the drives performances and Jos Steel Rolling Mill dc machine run-up characteristics using silicon control rectifier speed control for various results was presented graphically for dynamic study and This is recommendation for machines designers, engineers and operators of Jos Steel rolling mill industries.

KEY WORDS: *Rolling mills, Pull over mill, High reversing mill, Rectifier, Semiconductor, Transient, Filtration, Capacitor, Rheostat, Reactance.*

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Jos steel rolling mill direct current machine speed control using closed-loop silicon control rectifier speed control is presented. Jos steel rolling mill is one of the three inland rolling mills established by the Federal government of Nigeria to enhance the development of steel sub-sector. As part of the ongoing efforts to revive the nation's steel industry so that the country can commence steel production. No nation can really develop without the development of its steel industry. The pivot to this development of the steel industry is through research that calls for this research in the steel industry. Rolling mills are types of metal forming machinery that process various metals through sets of roll to reduce thickness, create uniform thickness, imprint a design or compact loose material. Three types of rolling mills are two high pull over mill that has two rolls with a constant direction of rotation around a horizontal axes, two high reversing mill that allow you to see the productivity improvement when using the two-high reversing mill and three-high rolling mill. Stress on Jos Steel Rolling Mill systems is increasing day by day, due to faults and sudden load change that constitutes negative threat to Jos Steel rolling mill stability. To maintain the plant quality services, Study was carried out to examine the capacity and transient stability of the Jos Steel Rolling Mill. The direct current (DC) machines are electro-mechanical energy converters in which the electrical energy is

exchanged with the supply load in the form of direct currents and voltages. [2, 3] Silicon controlled rectifier (SCR) which allows electricity to flow in one direction is used in a high-power control and has 3 terminal and 4 solid state layer semiconductor current controlling device, but with the added ability to be able to turn it on and off. [5, 6]

2.0 JOS STEEL ROLLING MILL DIRECT CURRENT MACHINES

Jos Steel Rolling Mill Direct Current machine is electro - mechanical energy converter by which the electrical energy is exchanged with supply load in the form of direct voltages and currents Jos Steel Rolling Mill plant direct current (DC) machine circuit diagram is as shown in figure1(Figure1a: Show the Circuit Diagram of Jos Steel Rolling Mill Direct Current shunt Connected Machine, Figure1b: Show the Circuit Diagram of Jos Steel Rolling Mill Direct Current Series Connected Machine and Figure1c: Show the Circuit Diagram of Jos Steel Rolling Mill Direct Current Compound Connected Machine) UNIPORT]. The direct current machine of Jos Steel Rolling Mill is an electronically control variable magnitude of DC component of voltage through controlled rectification of a sinusoidal alternating current (AC) supply. [4, 7, 8] There are three types of DC machines used; Series machine, Shunt machine, and Compound machine. The series DC machine was used for high starting torque and speed variation such as vacuum cleaner, air Compressor, cranes, and traction system. [1, 9, 10]

Jos Steel Rolling Mill closed-loop silicon-controlled rectifier (JSCR) used for high power control 3 terminal and 4 solid state layer semiconductor current controlling device. JSCR DC machine controller allows electricity to flow in one direction to turn the DC machine 'ON' and 'OFF'.

Jos Steel Rolling Mill DC machine Silicon control rectifier (JSCR) circuit diagram of Closed Loop Speed Control test and experiment as shown in figure 2 and 3respectively. This is so arranged as to provide only unidirectional flow of current to the DC machine from the alternating current (AC) supply. The half-wave, full-wave, single phase was used in the system. The AC point was control through the uses of SCR where the dc machine was fired to maintain the JSCR from firing during the initial period. The maximum DC voltage was equal to that provided by the basic diode circuit and may be reduced from maximum to zero. [3, 5, 11] Jos Steel Rolling Mill plant Direct Current (DC) machine transient control from zero to maximum varying the armature voltage while keeping the field voltage control constant. [4, 5, 12] The control element varies the power applied to the DC machine through the uses of JSCR. [2, 10] The JSCR is a solid-state device whose function is analogous to that of the grid-controlled thyatron tube. It passes current in one direction only and rectifies. It turns and passed current upon the receipt of a trigger signal on the control electrode known as gate. As it turns 'ON' JSCR continues to conduct until the polarity of voltage across reversed. [5, 12] The point during the positive half-cycle of the input current which the rectification turned 'ON' was adjusted by the timing of the applied trigger signal to the gate. The JSCR turned off at the end of the positive half-cycle as the polarity of the applied voltage reversed.

3.0 COMPONENT OF JOS STEEL ROLLING MILL DC MACHINE (JSCR) SPEED CONTROL

Jos Steel Rolling Mill DC machine Silicon control rectifier (JSCR) circuit diagram JSCR speed control has the following feature: It operate at 220Vac, Rectifies alternating current, varies DC machines by retarding the firing angle of JSCR and allows firing angle to change. The major components that form Jos Steel Rolling Mill DC machine JSCR speed control is as shown in figure3 circuit diagram.

Jos Steel Rolling Mills Speed Control; It is often necessary to control the speed and torque of DC machine. Applications for speed control range from computer equipment such as disc drives or heavy industry like Jos steel rolling mills. Speed control is essential in electric traction, where speed and tractive effort control is necessary for locomotives, shunt and separately excited machine, the speed and torque are related by machine equations. [2, 9]

$$\omega = \frac{V_t}{kI_f} - \frac{R_a}{(kI_f)^2} T \tag{1}$$

The speed can be varied by three means,

Varying supply voltage, V_t

Varying field current, I_f

Varying armature resistance, R_a (Speed reduction only by adding another resistance to R_a)

As TR_a is small compared to $(kI_f)^2$, then:

$$\omega = \frac{V_t}{kI_f} \tag{2}$$

Thus, the speed of such machine was control by changing supply voltage or the field current. The separated excited machine, the field was changed by a rheostat by power electronic means close- loop SCR. While the shunt machine a variable resistor was introduced in the shunt circuit. The field was weakening and the speed increased for smooth Jos steel rolling mill operation.

Consider a flux reaction of λ , λ being a fraction such as 0.1 for a 10% reduction. The rated speed was ω_1 and the new speed was ω_2 : then, [5, 8]

$$\omega_2 = \frac{E_{a2}}{E_{a1}} \frac{\phi_1}{\phi_2} \omega_1 = \frac{E_{a2}}{E_{a1}} \cdot \frac{I_{a2}}{I_{a1}} \omega_1 \tag{3}$$

$$= \frac{E_{a2}}{E_{a1}} \cdot \frac{1}{1-\lambda} \omega_1 \tag{4}$$

Where:

$$E_{a1} = V_t - I_{a1} R_a \tag{5}$$

$$E_{a2} = V_t - \frac{I_{a1} R_a}{1-\lambda} \tag{6}$$

The e.m.f equation

$$\frac{\omega_2}{\omega_1} = \frac{E_{a2}}{E_{a1}} \cdot \frac{\phi_1}{\phi_2} \tag{7}$$

The flux is proportional to field current:

$$\omega_2 = \frac{E_{a2}}{E_{a1}} \cdot I_{f1} \omega_1 \quad (8)$$

$$I_{f1} = \frac{V_t}{R_f} \quad (9)$$

$$I_{f2} = \frac{V_t}{R_f + R_{adj}} = \frac{V_t}{R_{tot}} \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{I_{f1}}{I_{f2}} = \frac{\frac{V_t}{R_f}}{\frac{V_t}{R_{tot}}} = \frac{R_{tot}}{R_f} \quad (11)$$

$$\Rightarrow R_{tot} = \frac{\omega_2}{\omega_1} \frac{E_{a1}}{E_{a2}} R_f \quad (12)$$

$$= \frac{N_2}{N_1} \frac{E_{a1}}{E_{a2}} R_f \quad (13)$$

Speed-torque equation of a series motor is as follows: [7, 9]

$$\omega = \frac{V_t}{k} \sqrt{\frac{k}{T} - \frac{R_{tot}}{k}} \quad (14)$$

Since $\frac{R_{tot}}{k}$ is small, then:

$$V_t \sqrt{k} \quad (15)$$

Squaring roots again, gives us,

$$\omega = \frac{V_t}{\sqrt{k\sqrt{T}}} \quad (16)$$

Squaring both sides

$$\omega^2 = \frac{V_t^2}{kT} \quad (17)$$

But:

$$T = kI^2 \quad (18)$$

Thus we have

$$\omega^2 = \frac{V_t^2}{k^2 I^2} \Rightarrow \omega = \frac{V_t}{kI} \quad (19)$$

When V_t is kept constant, the relationship between speed and armature current is a hyperbola graphically. There are two methods to control the speed: we can change the field or change the armature voltage (V_t).

Figure1a: Circuit Diagram of Jos Steel Rolling Mill Direct Current shunt Connected Machine UNIPORT]

Figure1b: Circuit Diagram of Jos Steel Rolling Mill Direct Current Series Connected Machine UNIPORT]

Figure1c: Circuit Diagram of Jos Steel Rolling Mill Direct Current Compound Connected Machine [UNIPORT]

Figure2: Jos Steel Rolling Mill Direct Current Machine Test Using Closed Loop Speed Control [2, 9]

Figure3: Jos Steel Rolling Mill DC machine closed-loop Silicon control rectifier (JSCR) Circuit Diagram [UNIPORT]
 (Where JSCR is Jos Steel Rolling Mill DC machine closed-loop Silicon control rectifier)

4.0 LABORATORY EXPERIMENT ON JOS STEEL ROLLING MILL DC MACHINE CLOSED-LOOP SILICON CONTROL RECTIFIER

The laboratory experiment was conducted in the [UNIPORT] standard laboratory. Jos Steel Rolling Mill DC machine Silicon control rectifier (**JSCR**) **Transformer** T_1 is autotransformer which changes the 220Vac terminal 2 and 1 to 300Vac terminal 3 and 1. The transformer is center tapped terminal 4 giving 200Vac between terminal 4 and 1 or terminal 4 and 3.

JSCR Capacitor C_1 and **Rheostat** R_1 Varying R_1 the phase angle voltage between terminal 4 and 5 change from zero to 140 degree lag.

JSCR Transformer T_1 Primary winding voltage between terminal 4 and 5 step down the secondary voltage of terminal 7 and 9 of the transformer T_2 varying rheostat R_1 The change from zero to 145degree with respect to the zero unit the 250volts output 1 and 3 of the transformer T_1

JSCR Diode D_1 and the potentiometer R_2 are the dc reference voltage terminal 6 and 1, this was vary from 0 to 120Vdc. (Closed loop control system).

JSCR Reactance “ X_L ” is the part of the JSCR that provide filtration for the smooth operation of the dc machine in the Jos Steel Rolling Mill plant and prevent heavy armature transient surge current terminal 3 and 10.

JSCR Silicon Control Rectifier (JSCR) The JSCR anode, cathode and gate are the terminal 10, 11 and 9. The AC voltage across the transformer “ T_2 ” at the terminal 7 and 9 cause the gate at the terminal 9 of the JSCR to trigger the JSCR on earlier and later in the cycle as setted on the rheostat “ R_1 ” control terminal 7 and is connected to terminal 11 of the JSCR for Closed loop system.

JSCR Armature ‘A’ Terminal 1 and 11 was connected to the armature of the dc machine terminal 11 and is positive with respect to terminal 1 at ground potential.

JSCR Capacitor “ C_2 ” The electrolytic filtering capacitor was connected across the dc machine and armature winding connected to terminal 8 and 1. Since the capacitor have to discharge through armature winding when the JSCR is not conducting and for the smooth running of the dc machine then terminal 8 and 11 was used for the smooth operation of the dc machine. The dc machine was observed to vibrate cooler than before because the capacitor absorbs the current peak during each cycle rather than the armature.

The figure 2 show Jos Steel Rolling Mill Direct Current Machine Test Using Closed Loop Speed Control and the control system as follows: (1) Set the desire speed (2) The controller control the speed (3) Compares the actual speed from tacho-generator (4) The current controller control the current from over current (5) Uses input current from the measuring device (6) The output from the current controller is converted to digital pulse (7) Converter driver (8) The converter output drives the motor (9) The field converter is a simple rectifier that provide a constant field current (10) Received Constant field current

The laboratory experiment was conducted in the UNIPORT standard laboratory which shows that as the rheostat ‘R’ was varied until armature voltage ‘ E_A ’ = 175Vdc. The effect upon the dc machine speed and the armature voltage ‘ E_A ’ shows that at low DC machine speed, the armature conduct late. The highest speed obtained was 3540 rev/min before the DC machine turned ‘OFF’. To provide filtration for the smooth operation of the DC machine in Jos Steel Rolling Mill, Silicon control rectifier (JSCR) reactance “ X_L ” filter choke was incorporated and connected to terminal 3 and 10 of the JSCR to provide filtration for the smooth operation of the DC machine in the Jos Steel Rolling Mill to prevent heavy armature transient surge current. A Silicon control rectifier capacitor “ C_2 ” the electrolytic filtering capacitor was connected across the dc machine and the armature winding was connected to terminal 8 and 1. This is because, the capacitor have to discharge through armature winding when the JSCR is not conducting and for the smooth running of the DC machine, the terminal 8 and 11 was used for the smooth operation of the DC machine instead of terminal 8 and 1. The capacitor absorbs

the current peak during each cycle rather than the armature and the dc machine vibrate cooler than before.

Table 1: Experimental Result Record of Jos Steel Rolling Mill Shunt DC Machine Silicon Control Rectifier (JSCR) Speed Control

E_A (volts)	I_A (amps)	Speed (rev/min)	Torque (Ibft.in)
200	0.34	1495	0
200	1.02	1424	3
200	1.73	1264	6
200	2.34	1219	9
200	2.93	1384	12
200	3.14	1414	15

Table2: Experimental Result Record of Jos Steel Rolling Mill Series DC Machine Silicon Control Rectifier (JSCR) Speed Control

E_A (volts)	I_A (amps)	Speed (rev/min)	Torque (Ibft.in)
200	0.63	5250	0
200	1.44	2552	3
200	2.23	2019	6
200	2.14	1734	9
200	2.24	1514	12
200	3.19	1433	15

Table3: Experimental Result Record of Jos Steel Rolling Mill Compound DC Machine Silicon Control Rectifier (JSCR) Speed Control

E_A (volts)	I_A (amps)	Speed (rev/min)	Torque (Ibft.in)
200	0.24	1450	0
200	0.84	1315	3
200	1.29	1245	6
200	2.69	1130	9
200	2.09	1115	12
200	2.99	1100	15

Table 4: Parameters in simulation of Jos Steel Rolling Mill Machine

Stator leakage inductance	2.59Mh
q-axis rotor leakage inductance	40.61Mh
d-axis rotor resistance	0.8113Ω
q-axis rotor resistance	1.6226Ω
q-axis magnetizing inductance	40.69Mh
d-axis magnetizing inductance	19.05mH
d-axis rotor leakage inductance	18.97mH
Load torque	7.63Nm
Motor inertial	0.01986Kgm ²
Rated voltage	230V(208V, 255V)

Source: [2, 9]

Figure 4: Graph of Stator Phase Currents against time of Jos Steel rolling mill at run-up Condition.

Figure 5: Graph of Motor Torque against Rotor Speed of Jos Steel rolling mill at run-up Condition.

Figure 6: Graph of Motor Torque against Time of Jos Steel rolling mill for Varying Stator Resistance.

Figure 7: Graph of Rotor Speed against time of Jos Steel rolling mill for Varying Equivalent Field Current.

Figure 8: Graph of Motor Torque against time of Jos Steel rolling mill for Varying Equivalent Field Current.

Figure 9: Graph of Electromagnetic Torque against Rotor Speed of Jos Steel rolling mill at run-up condition.

Figure 10: Graph of Power Factor against Stator Current of Jos Steel rolling mill at run-up condition.

The laboratory experiment conducted shows that as the rheostat 'R' was varied until armature voltage ' E_A ' = 175Vdc. Jos steel rolling mill speed of DC machine was control by changing supply voltage or the field current. The field was changed by a rheostat by power electronic means using close- loop Silicon Control Rectifiers Speed Control. While for the shunt machine, a variable resistor was introduced in the shunt circuit. The field was weakening and the speed increased for smooth Jos steel rolling mill operation. The effect upon the DC machine speed and the armature voltage ' E_A ' shows that at low DC machine speed, the armature conducts late. The highest speed obtained was

3540 rev/min before the DC machine turned 'OFF'. To provide filtration for the smooth operation of the DC machine in Jos Steel Rolling Mill closed-loop Silicon control rectifier (JSCR) reactance " X_L " filter choke was incorporated and connected to terminal 3 and 10 of the JSCR to provide filtration for the smooth operation of the DC machine in the Jos Steel Rolling Mill to prevent heavy armature transient surge current. A Silicon control rectifier capacitor " C_2 " the electrolytic filtering capacitor was connected across the DC machine and the armature winding was connected to terminal 8 and 1. This is because, the capacitor have to discharge through armature winding when the JSCR is not conducting and for the smooth running of the DC machine, the terminal 8 and 11 was used for the smooth operation of the DC machine instead of terminal 8 and 1. The capacitor of the JSCR absorbs the current peak during each cycle rather than the armature and machine vibrate cooler than before. The results were depicted graphically for dynamic study as follows: Figure 4 shows graph of stator phase currents against time at run-up condition, figure 5 shows graph of motor torque against rotor speed at run-up condition, figure 6 shows graph of motor torque against time for varying stator resistance, figure 7 shows graph of rotor speed against time for varying equivalent field current, figures 8 shows graph of motor torque against time for varying equivalent field current, figures 9 shows graph of electromagnetic torque against rotor speed at run-up condition and figure 10 shows graph of power factor against stator current at run-up condition of Jos steel rolling mill direct current machine speed control using closed-loop silicon control rectifier speed control

5.0 CONCLUSION

Jos Steel Rolling Mill Direct Current machine transient control using closed-loop silicon control rectifier speed control of the shunt, series and compound machines torque of the dc machine which is depends upon the product of the armature current and magnetic field. Experiment carried out reveal that, the shunt DC machine was observed to have constant speed because of its armature voltage and magnetic field remain unchanged from no-load to full-load. Jos steel rolling mill speed of DC machine was control by changing supply voltage or the field current. The field was changed by a rheostat by power electronic means using close- loop Silicon Control Rectifiers Speed Control. While for the shunt machine a variable resistor was introduced in the shunt circuit. The field was weakening and the speed increased for smooth Jos steel rolling mill operation.

A Silicon control rectifier capacitor " C_2 " the electrolytic filtering capacitor was connected across the DC machine and the armature winding was connected to terminal 8 and 1. This is because, the capacitor have to discharge through armature winding when the JSCR is not conducting and for the smooth running of the DC machine, the terminal 8 and 11 was used for the smooth operation of the dc machine instead of terminal 8 and 1. The capacitor absorbs the current peak during each cycle rather than the armature and the dc machine vibrate cooler than before.

The torque was very high for armature current for series DC machine as compare to shunt dc machine. The compound DC machine starting torque was higher than that of series DC machine due to the additional torque contributed by the shunt DC machine. The armature voltage, armature current and field current was recorded as $E_A = 195V$ dc, $I_A = 2.45A$ dc, $I_f = 250A$ dc. An Appreciable sparking at the brushes and appreciable machine vibration was noted and at the frequency of 60Hz.

Jos Steel Rolling Mill Shunt DC machine closed-loop Silicon Control Rectifier (JSCR) reactance " X_L " the filter choke was incorporated and connected to terminal 3 and 10 of the JSCR to provide filtration for the smooth operation of the DC machine in the Jos Steel Rolling Mill to prevent heavy armature transient surge current and Silicon Control Rectifier Capacitor " C_2 " the electrolytic filtering capacitor was connected across the DC machine and the armature winding was connected to terminal 8 and 1. Since the capacitor have to discharge through armature winding when the JSCR is not conducting and instead of terminal 8 and 1, It was re-connected to terminal 8 and 11 for the stability and smooth operation of the Jos Steel Rolling Mil machine. The Jos Steel Rolling Mill machine was noted to vibrate cooler than before because, the capacitor absorbs the current peak during each cycle rather than the armature. The effect upon the DC machine speed and the armature voltage ' E_A '= $175V$ dc was observed that at low DC machine speed, the armature conduct late at the speed of 3540 rev/min before the DC machine turned 'OFF'. Series DC machine should be used when high starting torque is requires like electric bus, train, Jos Steel Rolling Mill DC machine and heavy duty traction-application. The results were depicted graphically for dynamic study as follows: Figure 4 shows graph of stator phase currents against time at run-up condition, figure 5 shows graph of motor torque against rotor speed at run-up condition, figure 6 shows graph of motor torque against time for varying stator resistance, figure7shows graph of rotor speed against time for varying equivalent field current, figures 8 shows graph of motor torque against time for varying equivalent field current, figures 9 shows graph of electromagnetic torque against rotor speed at run-up condition and figure 10 shows graph of power factor against stator current at run-up condition of Jos steel rolling mill direct current machine speed control using closed-loop silicon control rectifier speed control This is recommended for machines designers, engineers and Jos steel rolling mill plant operators.

REFERENCES

- S.V.M.B. P. Kiran, C.H.A. Bharadwaj, "An Algorithm for the Analysis of the transient and Steady States in a DC motor," Int. J. Elec. Electronics Eng. (IJEET), vol.3-(1), pp.2231-5284, 2013.
- E. Chikumi, O.I. Okoro, "M.T. Khan, Concise Higher Eletrical Engineering" publisher, Juta and Company, Mercury Crescent, Wetton, Cape Town, South Africa, pp188, 2008.

Scientific and Engineering Letters

Volume 12 Issue 2, April-June 2024

ISSN: 2836-9483

Impact Factor: 6.72

Journal Homepage: <https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/letters>

Email: contact@americaserial.com

Official Journal of America Serial Publication

- Y. Hung, Weibing Gao, James C. Hung, "Variable Structure control: a survey", IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics, Vol.40, No. 1, pp. 2-22, February 1993.
- Atul Kumar Dewangan, Nibbedita Chakraborty, Sashi Shukla, Vinod Yadu, "PWM Based Automatic Closed Loop Speed Control of DC Motor" International Journal of Engineering Trends and Technology Volume 3 Issue 2, 2012.
- S. Weerasoorya and M.A Al-Sharkawi "Identification and control of a DC Motor using back-propagation neural networks" IEEE transactions on Energy Conversion, Vol.6, No.4 pp.663-669, December 1991.
- B. S. Sindura. B. N. Kartheek. "Speed Control of Induction Motor Using Cycloconverter" International Journal of Engineering Trends and Technology (IJETY), Vol. 4, Issue 4, April 2013.
- K. D. Atul, Nibbedita Chakraborty, Sashi Shukla, Vinod Yadu. "PWM Based Automatic Closed-Loop Control of DC Motor". International Journal of Engineering Trends and Technology, Vol. 3, Issue 8, 2012
- S. T. Snehlata, Santosh Kompelli. "Design and Implementation of DC Motor Speed Control Based on Pic Microcontroller", International Journal of Engineering and Computer Science Vol. 3, Issue 9, Page No. 8075-8079 September, 2014
- O.I. Okoro, "Transient Analysis of a Permanent Magnet Synchronous Machine (PMSM) with Damper windings", NEJRD, vol.3 No.4. pp 66-69. 2005.
- Y. Miyama, M. Ishizuka, H. Kometani, K. Akatsu, "Vibration reduction by applying carrier phase-shift PWM on dual three-phase windings Machine" In Proceedings of IEEE International Electric Machines Drives Conference (IEMDC), Miami, FL, USA, 21-24; pp. 5998-6004, May 2017.
- Z. Zhang, J. Shu, "Matlab-based Machines vector control simulation. In Proceedings of the 2010 3rd International Conference on Computer Science and Information Technology" Chengdu, China, 9-11; Volume 9, pp. 539-542, July 2010.

Scientific and Engineering Letters

Volume 12 Issue 2, April-June 2024

ISSN: 2836-9483

Impact Factor: 6.72

Journal Homepage: <https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/letters>

Email: contact@americaserial.com

Official Journal of America Serial Publication

T. Hara, T. Ajima, Y. Tanabe, M. Watanabe, K. Hoshino, K. Oyama, “Analysis of Vibration and Noise in Machines with Distributed Winding for the PWM Method”. IEEE Trans. Pp Ind. 54, 6042–6049, Appl. 2018.